

NOTES BRÈVES

Erra IV: (7-10). The text reads

- :7 *ša kak-ku la i-du-ú ša-lip pa-tar-šu*
 :8 *ša til-pa-nu la i-du-ú ma-lat ^{giš}qašat-su*
 :9 *ša šal-ta la i-du-ú ip-pu-ša la-ḫa-za*
 :10 *ša a-^fba¹-ra la i-du-ú iṣ-šu-riš i-šu-¹u-ú*

L. Cagni's transliteration (*L'Épopée*, 1969, p. 104, copy on Fig. 1) is followed including, and particularly, his reading of palaeographically uncertain *a-^fba¹-ra* of :10, which will be supported in the following. I propose to translate it "a wing" ("wings" for style, see Cagni, *The Poem of Erra*, 1977, p. 48). It is a variant of *abru* "wing" with a Sprossvoka, before *r* (*GAG* § 18 c).

The following pattern is shared by the four verses. (a) *ša* + noun¹ + *lā idū* verb + noun² (:7-9)/noun² + verb (:10). The word order of :10 sets it apart from :7-9 but compensates for its slight syntactic isolation by providing the verse with a vocalic ending thereby integrating it with the rest of the group phonetically. (In the interest of yet greater phonetic similarity one may perhaps prefer the variant *ta-ḫa-zu* (:9, ms. A), but we should probably not look to that much regularity in Akkadian poetry. [The examples of K. Hecker, *Untersuchungen zur akkadischen Epik*, 1974, p. 145, bottom, are of different kinds.]) (b) The four verses form two couplets, with the verbs of the first (:7-8) in the stative and with new subjects, whereas those of the second (:9-10) are in the present and retain the subjects of the first clauses ("He who heretofore did not know..., he now..."), which change intensifies the epic movement. (c) Within each verse both nouns are of the same narrowly circumscribed semantic field, :7-9 according to the clear text, :10 according to the present interpretation of Cagni's reading. This would be welcome even in case of an isolated :10; it is positively desirable when :10 is a member of a group that is constituted independently by features (a) and (b).

Translation. "He who knew nothing of weapons, his sword is drawn; he who knew nothing of shafts, his bow has plenty of them; he who knew nothing of fighting, does battle; he who knew nothing of wings, flies off like a bird."

M. TSEVAT (8 août 1986)

Enki et Ninḫursaġa 168. — Dans mon édition de ce mythe (*ZA* 74 [1984] 1 sqq.), je notais (p. 23, n. 44 et p. 42) que l'expression *^den-ki-ke₄ igi-ni im-ma-an-sig₇-sig₇* (...), « Enki "verdit" ses yeux », n'est pas claire. Je serais maintenant tenté d'y voir un « jeu de mots » sur le ND (parlant l) *^digi-sig₇-sig₇*, « à la face verte / aux yeux verts » (cf. W. G. Lambert, *RLA* 5, 44 s.v.), un « grand jardinier » d'An (An-Anum I 92 et W. Farber, *Ištar und Dumuzi Ia* 68) ou d'Enlil (*BBR* 2, 27 II 7 // ; *KAR* 177 rev. I 22 sq. et *AMT* 6, 6, 9), quoique ce nom ne soit, à ma connaissance, pas attesté à époque ancienne.

P. ATTINGER (octobre 1986)

A Drt form of *pahāru*.—The letter fragment M. 7538, newly joined to *ARM* 1 69 and recently published by Durand and Charpin in *MARI* 4, p. 313, fig. 7, contains an example of a Drt form (Whiting, *OrNS* 50 [1981], 1-39) of the verb *pahāru* "to assemble", "to gather together". Lines 13-19 of the text contain the following: *ša-ab ma-a-tim ša-a-ti ka-li-ša ù lú.mes [T]u-ru-uk-ku-ú ša it-ti-šu-nu up-ta-ha-ah-hi-ru-ma [i]-na a-lim Ik-ka-al-lim^{KI} [š]a ma-a-at A-ha-zi-im^{KI} a-na pa-an I[š-me-^dD]a-gan [š]a-[ak]-nu* "the troops of that entire country and the Turukkeans who were with them joined together and placed themselves in the city of Ikkallum of the land of Ahazum to oppose Išme-Dagan". The form *up-ta-ha-ah-hi-ru* in line 15 is a paradigmatic Drt preterite. In *OrNS* 50 [1981], 31-32, n. 111-15 and 34, n. 123, it was suggested that the Drt serves (secondarily) to differentiate the reciprocal/reflexive of the factitive D stem from the passive of the D stem (expressed by the Dt).

The verb *pahāru* is not, strictly speaking, a stative verb, but represents an intransitive action. The D stem, however, functions like a factitive in that it expresses the corresponding transitive action and the placing of something in the condition indicated by the B-stem stative (*pahir* "gathered [together]"). Thus we have *pahāru* "to gather (together), to assemble" (intransitive) and *puhhuru* "to collect, to assemble" (transitive) and it can be seen that *pahāru* behaves like a stative verb: B stem = to come into the condition indicated by the B stative and D stem = to put into the condition indicated by the B stative. We could therefore expect a Drt form to exist and to mark the reciprocal/reflexive in contrast to the Dt passive.

First we can ask if the form can be emended by eliminating the additional *-ha-* sign. Doing so results in two possible forms, a D perfect or a Dt preterite. A D perfect seems unlikely since there is no object indicated for the transitive verb. A Dt passive is possible, especially in connection with *[š]a-[ak]-nu* in line 19, "(they) were collected and... were placed", but there is no agent (logical subject) of this action either expressed or implied elsewhere in the letter. The most straightforward solution is to accept the form *uptahahirū* as a Drt reflexive "they collected themselves".

Finally, the B stem of *pahāru* "gather", "sich versammeln", has a reciprocal/reflexive nuance inherent in its meaning; the action is performed by the individual members of the subject to and for themselves and each other, and "gather" implies "gather themselves together". Thus there is essentially no difference between the B stem "gather" and the Drt reciprocal/reflexive "collect themselves", and the two forms are semantically equivalent. That this is, in fact, the case is indicated by lines 23-25 of the same letter where the exact same expression as found in lines 13-15 is repeated but with the B preterite *iphurū* replacing the Drt preterite *uptahahirū*.

The form *uptahahirū* is a useful addition to the inventory of Akkadian verbal forms with the second radical reduplicated in that it conforms to the predicted pattern of usage and tends to confirm that these rare (and in this case, unnecessary) forms were still a productive part of the morphological repertoire during the Old Babylonian period.

Robert M. WHITING

Ugarit dans les textes d'Ebla ? — Dans la « Liste de Noms géographiques », dont les douze premières cases ne sont conservées que dans le manuscrit provenant d'Ebla, voir G. Pettinato, *Or* 47, 1978, p. 68 s., on lit au n° 5 : *U₆-ga-ra-a^{KI}*, qui doit être identifiée, selon G. Pettinato (*Atti I Congresso Internazionale di Studi Fenici e Punici I*, Roma, 1983, p. 108), avec Ugarit. Mais le signe *U₆(EZEN × AN)* exprime *h/ḫu*, comme l'a montré M. Krebernik, *ZA* 72, 1982, p. 219, ou même *wu*, voir *U₆-ra-ne/na-a^{KI}*, *Wu-ra-nu^{KI}*, dans les citations rassemblées par F. M. Fales, *MARI* 3, 1983, p. 269. L'identification que Pettinato propose semble donc improbable. D'autre part il serait étonnant que la « Liste de Noms géographiques » s'ouvre par des noms de villes de la côte méditerranéenne, étant donné qu'elle a été sûrement composée en Mésopotamie, et non à Ebla comme le pense Pettinato, *Testi lessicali mono-*